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ENHANCING SOCIAL MEDIA MARKETING EFFICIENCY THROUGH ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE

Abstract

Artificial intelligence (AI) has become integral to modern social media marketing, transforming how businesses engage with consumers, analyze data, and optimize strategies. AI tools enable personalized content, automate customer interactions through chatbots, and boost engagement rates. (Kaplan & Haenlein, 2019). Advances in machine learning, natural language processing, and predictive analytics have made marketing campaigns more effective by providing real-time insights into consumer behavior and social media trends. campaigns (Russell & Norvig, 2021). AI helps brands enhance customer experiences by automating customer service, optimizing ad placements, and analyzing vast amounts of social media data for targeted advertising. Research question: How can artificial intelligence (AI) tools be effectively utilized to enhance marketing efficiency in social media campaigns?

The aim of the paper- to explore AI's role in increasing social media marketing campaigns efficiency. Research method 7 qualitative interviews with Lithuanian marketing professionals, AI specialists, and social media strategists. The research identified key AI tools such as content personalization platforms, predictive analytics, and automated ad systems that streamline marketing processes and improve campaign outcomes. Experts highlighted benefits like more automation in the content, possibility of deeper personalization, improved customer engagement and media campaigns efficiency, but also noted challenges, including ethical concerns, data privacy issues, and technical integration hurdles. The study offers practical recommendations for leveraging AI effectively in social media marketing. As AI continues to develop, its strategic implementation will be crucial for staying competitive and maximizing marketing ROI in the dynamic social media landscape.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Social Media Marketing, Personalization, Automation, Content creation

Introduction

AI technologies have been in use for more than half a century, but their application in marketing remains a subject of scientific debate and research. A number of studies have been carried out. On AI tools in communication, marketing and commerce. In the global context, various scholars have investigated the application and impact of artificial intelligence (AI) across diverse domains. Kaplan and Haenlein (2019) provided a comprehensive conceptual framework for understanding AI in business, highlighting its transformative role in decision-making, customer interaction, and operational efficiency. Similarly, Brynjolfsson and McAfee (2017) examined the economic implications of AI technologies, emphasizing how machine learning and automation are reshaping industries by improving productivity and enabling new business models. Further expanding this view, Davenport and Ronanki (2018) analyzed how organizations implement AI, categorizing use cases

into process automation, cognitive insight, and cognitive engagement. Their findings suggest that while full-scale AI integration remains limited, targeted applications yield measurable benefits. In the retail and marketing sectors, Dwivedi et al. (2021) Mohammed et al. (2024) explored the use of AI in personalizing customer experiences, demonstrating how data-driven recommendations and predictive analytics enhance consumer satisfaction and loyalty. Meanwhile, Taddy (2019) discussed AI's role in analyzing unstructured data such as text and images, which is particularly useful in e-commerce and social media platforms. Kietzmann et al. (2018) made research on the role of AI in automating marketing workflows and decision-making processes, demonstrating that machine learning algorithms can optimize ad targeting and campaign performance. Furthermore, Jarek and Mazurek (2019) highlighted the effectiveness of AI-powered chatbots in social media platforms, improving customer service responsiveness and brand interaction. Wamba-Taguimdje et al. (2020) analyzed how predictive analytics and data mining through AI can guide marketers in crafting content that aligns with user preferences and behavior patterns. Lastly, O'Neil (2016) warned of the potential biases and ethical concerns arising from opaque AI algorithms, urging for transparency and accountability in AI system design. Collectively, these studies indicate that AI continues to expand its influence globally, offering significant advantages for business and marketing, while simultaneously posing new challenges for society and governance. However, there is a lack of research examining how AI tools affect the social media marketing efficiency. Since most companies have not yet embraced the benefits of AI, there may be a lack of information and evidence. Therefore, it is important to explore AI's functionalities. Research Question: How can artificial intelligence (AI) tools be effectively utilized to enhance the efficiency of social media marketing, and what are the key benefits and challenges associated with their application across different marketing functions?

Aim of the Paper- to investigate the role of artificial intelligence in enhancing the efficiency of social media marketing and to examine the potential of specific AI tools in optimizing social media marketing strategies and practices.

Objectives:

1. To examine the use of AI tools specifically within the context of social media marketing.
2. To evaluate the effectiveness of selected AI tools in improving social media marketing efficiency.
3. To identify the key challenges and advantages related to the use of AI in various social media marketing functions.

Research Methods: Theoretical methods: Analysis, synthesis, comparison, evaluation, and interpretation of scientific literature. Empirical method: Qualitative research through expert interviews to gain insights into the practical application and impact of AI tools in social media marketing.

1. Literature review

According to Encyclopaedia Britannica (2025), artificial intelligence is "the ability of a digital computer or computer-controlled robot to perform tasks normally

associated with human beings." The term is often used to refer to systems characterized by intellectual processes, such as memory, reasoning, problem-solving, generalization, and learning from previous experience. However, this definition does not fully capture the capabilities and essence of AI. According to this definition, every computer is an AI system because it possesses mental capabilities, such as a large memory, the ability to store and retrieve text, and the ability to solve mathematical equations. However, the goal of AI is not only to behave intelligently, but also to solve complex, high-level problems (Ertel, 2021). According to E. Rich (1985), "Artificial intelligence is the science of getting computers to do things that humans can do better." AI includes activities such as problem solving, natural language understanding, perception, and science. Given the human-like capabilities of AI tools, the term makes sense because AI is distinguished by its ability to accumulate knowledge, learn from experience, predict courses of action, solve problems, recognize human language, and interpret visual information. The main branches of AI are currently symbolic learning and machine learning, which analyze and understand data to provide solutions and outcomes (Chandula, 2020).

Fig.1. Hierarchy of AI technologies

Source: (Chandula, 2020).

2. Using AI in social media marketing

The rapid development of information technology and cognitive machine learning concepts has enabled the widespread use of artificial intelligence (AI) systems in business, improving work efficiency (Gutiérrez & Rodríguez, 2020). According to research conducted by Shatalov (2023), AI is used in marketing for the following reasons: 59% for improving customer service, 49% for improving productivity, and 44% for achieving profitable investments. AI enables data-driven offers of the most relevant product options for customers and the personalization of messages on social networks, thus improving interaction with brands. AI can also

provide more accurate information on customer behavior and needs. It is a fast and effective way to interact with customers on social networks to ensure their satisfaction and personalize communication solutions (Gutiérrez & Rodríguez, 2020). All of this reflects marketing effectiveness and company profitability. One of the most significant ways AI is transforming marketing is through data analytics. The amount of consumer data today is vast, beyond the capacity of a single human. AI can analyze this data, identifying patterns and trends that marketers can use to improve marketing effectiveness. Another important aspect of AI is automation. Machine learning algorithms can write advertising copy and create visual content tailored to users' different needs on social networks. This ensures the relevance and effectiveness of advertising while saving time. By analyzing data, AI helps practitioners identify effective and ineffective aspects of their activities. This enables data-driven decision-making and optimization of advertising to maximize its social and economic impact. Additionally, AI-based predictive analytics helps practitioners to forecast future market trends and consumer behaviour, allowing them to always be visible and a few steps ahead of competitors (Lee and Lin, 2005).

One of the challenges of implementing technology is ensuring data security. To implement customer personalization, companies must obtain private customer information, such as date of birth, gender, place of residence, and contact details. Improper handling or leakage of this data can have serious consequences for consumers and businesses alike. Inadequate protection can lead to unintended access, theft, or leakage of data, which increases the risk of losing customer trust and raises ethical and privacy concerns (Agadzianian, 2024).

Thus, some of the main applications of AI in marketing include data collection and analysis, automation, target audience segmentation, and visual and textual content creation. Using AI in marketing activities increases efficiency, boosts conversions, and enables professionals to focus on tasks requiring human attention and expertise.

3. Deatalisation of AI usage in Social Media Marketing

3.1. Personalisation tools

Personalisation through Artificial Intelligence (AI) technologies is becoming a key competitive advantage as a way to quickly and efficiently meet consumers' expectations, save time and attract attention (Karnilavičiūtė, 2021). This process is based on the creation of personalised content that responds to the needs of specific customers (Gutierrez and Rodriguez, 2020). At the heart of personalisation strategies are machine learning algorithms that analyse consumer data. They allow companies to target marketing content to specific audiences, ensuring that consumers see advertising that is relevant to them. AI analyses a wide range of information sources: consumer behaviour on a website, purchase history, interaction with a brand, reviews, clicks. Advertising offers on social networks are based on more than two hundred parameters. Users are presented to the algorithms as multidimensional data sets, which are analysed by neural networks. They independently determine which ads are most likely to attract the attention of a given user (Gutierrez and Rodriguez, 2020). Following the principles of information segmentation, the AI compares the behaviour

of a specific user with data from thousands of other users, looking for behavioural similarities. When relevant correlations are found, the system provides personalised recommendations (Starostin, 2018). According to Accenture (2024) statistics, it can be said that more than 90% of people are more likely to choose brands that take into account their opinions and needs (Dogadkina, 2023). The ability to create relevant personalised advertising content that resonates with audiences not only increases sales and improves the effectiveness of marketing strategies, but from the customer's point of view, it is also an opportunity to make the shopping experience and the selection of goods and services more convenient. The better the understanding of customer behaviour and consumption trends, the better it will be possible to satisfy desires and offer products. Artificial intelligence offers information and suggestions based on customer data and determines what type of content works best. For marketers, AI insights in personalisation and segmentation help them improve strategies and content for better results.

There are many AI personalisation tools (see Table 1) that are particularly effective in social media marketing.

Table 1

Effectiveness of AI personalisation and automation tools in social media marketing

Tool	Main function	Personalisation effect	Performance indicators
Meta Ads	Segmentation and real-time targeting of personalised ads based on user behaviour	High level of precision in audience selection, real-time response to consumer behaviour	CTR increase of up to 35%, ROI increase of 25% (Meta Business Insights, 2024)
Google Ads	Generation of personalised ads based on search, location and behavioural data	Increases ad relevance and reduces unnecessary click-through costs	30% increase in conversions, 18% decrease in CPC (Google Ads Benchmark Report, 2024)
HubSpot	Marketing process automation - content creation, personalisation, data analysis and forecasting.	Personalised content based on customer data analysis.	77% of professionals say AI helps personalise content, 70% say AI improves customer experience, 56% say AI makes content more effective (Zenon, 2024).
Mailchimp AI	Email automation and behavioural audience segmentation.	Personalised offers and optimal sending times based on user behaviour.	Open rate +50%, conversion +22%, saving an average of 10 hours per campaign (Bhattacharya, 2025).
MoEngage	Multichannel engagement & campaign automation	Personalised messages in email, push, SMS, in-app	Recognised by Customers' Choice on G2 and Gartner platforms
Omneky Smart Ads / Campaign Launcher	Ad creation, testing and automated ad management	Transparent, automatically generated and tested advertising options	Used in Meta, Google, TikTok campaigns from 2025.
Insider	Personalised content and ads on websites, apps	Personalised product/offer displays for users	Ranked among the top 10 personalised solutions on the market

Source: elaborated by the author

Table 1 shows the artificial intelligence (AI) tools used for social media marketing to personalize communication with consumers. These tools use advanced technologies, such as machine learning and consumer behavior analysis, to automate content creation, audience segmentation, and personalized offers. The personalization algorithms built into Meta Ads, Google Ads, Mailchimp AI, and other platforms allow for precise content targeting based on user behavior and interests. This is particularly important in social media marketing, where real-time solutions and personalized communication are key to campaign success. For instance, Mailchimp AI segments audiences based on behavior and automates email delivery, thereby increasing open rates by 50%, conversion rates by 22%, and reducing average campaign execution time. HubSpot's content personalization and customer data analytics improve the overall customer experience. MoEngage focuses on multichannel communication, including social networks and personalized messaging. Omneky Smart Ads stands out because it automatically generates and tests adverts on different social media platforms, such as Meta, Google, and TikTok. Insider dynamically tailors content to each user based on their behavior and preferences.

3.2 Textual content generation tools

ChatGPT, developed by OpenAI, is one of the most advanced AI text generation tools and is particularly appreciated in social media marketing. This natural language processing model generates text based on provided data and context, enabling the swift creation of tailored, engaging, and relevant content for target audiences. Trained on a dataset of 300 billion words from online sources, books, and articles, ChatGPT can generate content ranging from advertising slogans to brand-reflective scripts (Rudolph et al., 2023).

On social media platforms, where speed, visuals, and audience engagement are important, ChatGPT is becoming an indispensable tool for creating organic and promotional content. Before generating text, the model analyzes successful and unsuccessful campaigns, identifying their strengths and weaknesses to help optimize the effectiveness of new content. Through its personalization capabilities, ChatGPT tailors messages to specific target groups according to their behavior, interests, and needs.

Additionally, ChatGPT acts as an idea generator in creative sessions. It suggests alternative campaign angles, stylistic variations, and rhetorical patterns that may be overlooked by the average person (Tautvydienė & Morkevičienė, 2023). Thus, ChatGPT becomes a creative partner, not just a content creator.

In today's social networking space, where emotions and creativity influence audience engagement and purchasing decisions, the AI's ability to produce impactful content is strategically important. Posts written by the AI can trigger an emotional response, encouraging comments, shares, and views. AI writing tools (see Table 1.2) enable users to quickly generate different versions of a message, test their impact, and select the most effective one, thereby saving time and maximizing the ROI of campaigns (Kiseleva, 2018).

Table 2*Effectiveness of artificial intelligence tools for generating textual content in marketing*

Tool	Main function	Effect	Performance indicators
ChatGPT	Generates textual and visual content, personalises messages, analyses data, suggests strategies.	Helps create tailored content for target audiences, optimises communication, supports real-time interaction.	Content creation performance +30-45%, 73% of companies satisfied with results (Fomenko, 2025).
Jasper	Automates the creation of advertising texts, emails and product descriptions.	Maintains brand tone and style, increases writing speed.	Content creation costs reduced by 30%, 67% of users save 5+ hrs/save (Bhattacharya, 2025).
Claude	Text generation, conversation analysis, processing long documents.	Acts as a creative and strategic partner for content planning.	Used for content editing, analysis and personalisation (Anthropic, 2025).
Google Gemini	Extracts information from texts: emotions, themes, relationships, moods.	Accelerates content analysis and personalisation based on semantic context.	Reduces analysis time by 50% and increases sales revenue by 5% (Enlyft, 2025).
Microsoft Copilot	Integrated into Microsoft 365 - helps you write, create, edit.	Increases work efficiency, offers personalised assistance in document preparation.	Helps save time and ensures a consistent style (Microsoft, 2024).
DeepSeek	Searches and analyses marketing and social media content in real time.	Allows you to identify relevant topics and optimise the direction of content .	Improves decision-making in campaigns, improves engagement (DeepSeek AI, 2025).
Grammarly	Text correction, tone analysis, stylistics.	Ensures professional and inclusive text, avoids mistakes.	Saves 19 working days/year, 30 million daily users (Smalley, 2023).

Source: elaborated by the author

Table 2 shows the most popular Internet of Things (AI) tools currently in use for creating and personalizing textual content for social media marketing. These tools, including ChatGPT, Claude, Jasper, and Gemini, automate creative processes and help generate targeted, engaging, and stylistically consistent content. Integrations with everyday platforms, such as Microsoft Copilot and Grammarly, make these solutions even more convenient. Studies and user surveys demonstrate that these tools can significantly increase productivity, reduce development costs, and enhance audience engagement.

3.3. Visual content generation tools

Image generation is currently one of the most advanced areas of artificial intelligence, enabling new opportunities in the information, creative and communication industries. Image generators can be used as creative tools to generate new and unique images. In the creation of advertising content, they can help to generate original images that quickly capture the attention of customers. (Tautvydienė and Morkevičienė, 2023) AI visual generation models (see Table 3) show great potential in content marketing and increase the effectiveness of content creation.

Table 3

Visual content generation of artificial intelligence tools in social media marketing

Tool	Main function	Performance indicators
DALL-E	A model that generates high quality images from textual descriptions. Used for illustrations, social media content, advertising and conceptual design.	Swedish fintech company Klarna has integrated "DALL-E and MidJourney into its marketing operations, saving SEK 1.5 million in the first quarter of 2024. The company reduced its image development time from 6 weeks to 7 days. In addition, the company has reduced marketing costs, with 37% savings from (Kelly, 2024).
Canva AI	Uses AI to automate the design process by suggesting templates, generating images and optimising visual elements. Tailored for social media content, ads and presentations.	According to Canva platform statistics, 78% of professionals believe AI is important for long-term content strategy and 70% say it increases the productivity of teams. 94% agreed that AI is good for the creative process.
Designify	Automatically removes backgrounds, improves image quality and applies stylistic effects, making it easier to create visuals for social media and advertising.	According to recent data, 61% of marketers believe that AI tools like Designify help them to improve performance. In addition, companies deploying AI solutions, can expect a 30% reduction in marketing spend (Perelman, 2024).
MidJourney	A tool for generating high-quality images from textual descriptions.	Around 32% of Midjourney users use the tool for graphic design and content creation, demonstrating its effectiveness in practical applications. (10 Midjourney Statistics Demonstrating Why its Better Than Other AI Art Generators, 2024) Ukrainian startup Headway, using Midjourney in combination with other AI tools, has increased the performance of its video ads by 40%, reaching a 3.3 billion views in the first half of 2024 (O'Reilly, 2024)

Tool	Main function	Performance indicators
Sora OpenAI	It is a cutting-edge text and video model that enables the creation of high- quality, realistic videos from simple text queries.	"Sora is a useful tool for marketing when budgets are limited and video content needs to be short. Based on a study conducted in 2023 "Capgemini survey in 2023, 59% of executives around the world are already using this artificial intelligence for images and video to create video and video images. A further 12% plan to do so in the next 6-12 months (Lebow, 2024)

Source: elaborated by the author.

Table 3 shows the most popular AI tools for generating and editing visuals for social media marketing. Most of the tools, such as DALL-E, Canva AI, MidJourney, and Runway ML, allow for a significant reduction in the time and cost of creating images or videos, as well as an increase in audience engagement. Using AI for design and content creation gives businesses a strategic advantage by enabling them to deliver content more efficiently and quickly. However, experts have pointed out that AI capabilities are not yet ideal and depend on human input. AI sometimes lacks creativity and often needs a personal touch.

3.4 Prediction and data analysis tools

Forecasting and analysis tools in marketing anticipate future trends, consumer behaviour, market developments. They are able to forecast sales and customer retention rates, the effectiveness of advertising campaigns and optimise budgets. Prediction and analysis tools are actively used in marketing strategy and are divided into feeling AI and thinking AI (Lee et al. 2016; Mende, 2019).

Sentiment AI works in a similar way to personalisation tools, and is used to predict and anticipate customers' next steps and build long-term relationships with them, as it is able to recognise and respond to emotions. Marketing is closely linked to emotions, feedback, comments and complaints. Emotional AI analyses and converts all this into data to create the most appropriate customer service strategy and approach. Emotional AI identifies the customer's profile, needs and current favourite product. Customer understanding is a key difference from thinking AI (Lee et al. 2016; Mende, 2019). Thinking AI analyses information through the prism of human logical reasoning, it is able to anticipate a problem and provide a solution, analyse customer actions, process large amounts of data to identify hidden relationships and make future predictions based on rational analysis. Using regression models that predict how variables interact with each other and decision trees - structured decision-making based on different scenarios - AI can analyse sales data and predict which goods and services will be popular next season (Lee et al. 2016; Mende, 2019). Thinking AI creates multiple future scenarios based on previous data and can choose the best sequence of actions or decision, identifying the optimal pattern of action that influences different outcomes. By analysing competitors in a selected market, foresight tools assess their strategies and operating models, compare competitors and

draw conclusions, and help to find new opportunities in specific markets (Lee et al. 2016; Mende, 2019).

Artificial intelligence efficiently processes information, highlighting key trends, allowing marketers to tailor their strategies to the needs of the target audience. Such tools help to develop social media marketing strategies, calculating possible next steps and future forecasts in real time, reacting quickly to environmental factors and changes in consumer behaviour (Agajanian, 2024). However, artificial intelligence can lead to dependence on technology, and in the event of failure, information and business processes can be lost. There is also a shortage of skilled big data professionals, which can lead to errors in analysis and decisions. These risks highlight the importance of implementing security strategies, managing data properly and ensuring compliance with applicable legal regulations (Agajanian, 2024). Despite the challenges, data analysis tools (Table 4) are considered as key helpers for marketers due to their ability to analyse data in just seconds and provide predictive insights.

Table 4

AI forecasting tools applied in social media marketing

Tool	Main function	Effect	Performance indicators
Google Cloud AI	Using machine learning to analyse marketing data, predict sales trends and consumer behaviour	Helps optimise advertising campaigns.	According to a Google Cloud study, OnlineSales.ai reduced the time it takes to query data from 8 seconds to 3 seconds by using Google Cloud's BigQuery artificial intelligence tool, which enabled faster analysis and more effective targeting. In addition, using the Cloud Load Balancing tool, the time to serve an ad on was reduced by 30% from 80 ms to 55 ms.
Tableau with AI	A tool for data visualisation and marketing analytics	Helps visualise data for analysis	A law firm has experienced a 40% reduction in work after integrating Einstein Analytics into its system
Meta Advantage+	Automatically optimises the delivery of advertising campaigns using machine learning, predicts the best audience.	Using automated optimisation can reduce costs and increase conversions without manual work.	According to Meta, in 2024, advertisers using Advantage+ saw an average 20% higher ROAS and 29% lower CPA.
Crimsn Hexagn (Brandwatch)	Uses AI to predict trends and analyse consumer opinions on social networks	Helps to discern emerging themes and customer sentiment for marketing decisions.	With this tool, brands can respond faster to crises and increase audience engagement by up to 37%.

Source: elaborated by the author

AI-based predictive tools are becoming increasingly important in social media marketing. They not only analyse consumer behaviour but also predict future purchasing decisions, content trends or campaign performance. Some of the most popular tools include Google Cloud AI, Amazon Forecast, H2O.ai, Meta Advantage+ and Brandwatch. These tools help you reduce workload, optimise budgets and better target audiences. Businesses that integrate these solutions tend to see higher ROAS, lower CPA and faster strategic marketing decisions. By analysing company performance data, AI can help marketers identify which aspects of their campaigns are working and which need improvement. This allows them to make data-driven decisions and optimise campaigns to maximise their social and economic impact. In addition, AI-based predictive analytics can help practitioners anticipate future trends and consumer behaviour, allowing them to stay ahead of competitors and make more informed marketing decisions (Шевченко et al. 2024).

Methodology

This empirical study aimed to investigate how artificial intelligence is applied in practice and to assess its impact on marketing activities such as personalisation, visual and textual design, automation, data analysis and prediction.

The research adopted a qualitative research approach in the form of semi-structured interviews with experts. The application of AI tools in marketing practice is a dynamic, new and multifaceted topic that cannot be adequately explored through quantitative research alone. The qualitative approach chosen allows the use of AI tools to be analysed through the subjective experiences and opinions of the research participants. According to Bitin (2006), qualitative research focuses on understanding the essence of a phenomenon, and allows us to delve deeper into human activity and context in the natural environment. This approach is useful for analysing phenomena that have not yet been explored, where an interpretative approach is needed (Žydžiūnaitė and Sabaliauskas, 2017).

Expert interviews are a specific type of interview designed to gather professional or institutional experience with individuals who are considered to be experts in the field of the research question, demonstrating exceptional knowledge and experience. Such interviews help to reveal information based on facts, interpretations and analysis (Creswell, 2018; Kumar, 2019), (Meuser and Nagel 2009). The subject of the research requires insights from professionals - practitioners, not consumers - who apply AI tools directly in their work and are able to assess their effectiveness, challenges and practical benefits. The choice of this type of interviews allows for a deeper understanding of marketers' attitudes towards AI tools and the possibilities of applying them in practice. An expert is a person with exceptional theoretical knowledge and accumulated professional experience in a particular field, demonstrating a high level of competence and recognized by other members of the community or institutions (Gaižauskaitė and Valavičienė, 2016), (Bogner et al., 2009). Sample: 7 marketing experts in Lithuania who use AI tools for marketing purposes were interviewed during the qualitative research. A purposive sampling approach was used to select candidates with significant insights into the phenomenon under study (Butinas, 2006). The selected respondents - marketing professionals

working in different organisations - not only use AI tools in practice, but also actively participate in their implementation, evaluation and creative application processes. The sample size was set to obtain more detailed information, and new interviews were conducted until the opinions became repetitive and did not reveal new aspects. All experts were selected on the basis of their work experience and the use of artificial intelligence, and candidates were contacted via the LinkedIn platform. In order to ensure a diversity of responses and opinions, the survey sample was made up of professionals working in organisations of different sizes and in different roles.

The research questions were designed to uncover marketers' experiences with artificial intelligence, how these tools contribute to marketing effectiveness, their advantages and disadvantages, and the challenges in implementing them. The survey data collection took place in March-April 2025.

Research findings

The aim of the qualitative research was to analyse the practice of applying artificial intelligence (AI) tools in social media marketing, based on the experience of Lithuanian specialists. The study revealed the main areas of AI use, advantages, challenges, ethical aspects in Social Media Marketing.

Expert interviews revealed that AI tools are most commonly used for content creation (text, images, videos), data analysis, personalisation, and predicting consumer behaviour. Respondents stressed that these tools allow them to process information more quickly, create more effective content and make decisions based on data.

The most frequently mentioned tools are ChatGPT, MidJourney, Claude, Sora, Heygen, Grok, Canva AI. These tools are used to generate textual, visual and video content, as well as to analyse consumer behaviour and predict decisions.

Personalisation tools such as Meta Ads, Google Ads allow you to tailor content to specific audiences based on their behaviour and needs. Automation solutions - especially in email marketing - allow you to reduce manual tasks and increase the volume of campaigns.

Experts stress that AI helps to analyse large amounts of data, but the quality of the result depends on the skills of the user. Properly structured data can lead to targeted insights and predictions.

The most frequently cited benefits by experts are productivity gains, time savings, idea generation and automation of the creative process. The main challenges in social media marketing are the training of staff, the abundance of tools, the rapid development of technology and the need for investment. The lack of authenticity and creativity and the high demands on user skills. It takes time to adapt to changing technologies and develop the ability to select the right tools.

Discussion

The results of the study are in line with recent trends in AI marketing, also highlighted by Starostin (2018), Gutierrez and Rodriguez (2020), Zhang et al. (2023), Petrauskaite and Zemkauskaite (2024). AI tools act as facilitators to optimise social media marketing activities, but their effectiveness depends on people's ability to apply them properly. Deployment requires investment and competences, but the

greatest benefits can be seen in the areas of visual and textual content generation, analysis and campaign personalisation.

Each expert has found his or her own effective tools that have increased marketing effectiveness in different ways: data analysis is easier, routine work is reduced, personalisation is more accurate, newsletter marketing has improved, and content for marketing campaigns is created faster and in greater quantities. In addition, insights were provided on how to use the tools appropriately to get a quality result and to protect user confidentiality. While significant challenges to the deployment of AI have been identified, such as investment, training of staff, high information flow and constant analysis of tools, experts and authors of scientific sources predict an increase in the use of AI (Krasnolutska, 2024), the emergence and development of AI agents (Castillo and Taherdoost, 2023), the reduction of specialist teams and the evolution of professions.

Conclusions

1. Artificial Intelligence (AI) is becoming a strategic tool in social media marketing, enabling more effective content creation, analysis and personalisation, and optimising communication processes. The results of the study show that IoT solutions in Lithuania have already been integrated into the daily practice of many marketers, especially in the management of social networks.

2. AI-based tools such as ChatGPT, MidJourney, Jasper, Sora or Canva AI help develop creative and visual content that is strategically tailored to different audiences. Such tools not only reduce content creation time, but also improve audience engagement on social networks, contributing to higher conversion and user loyalty. The tools are also used as idea generators that enhance the creative process of content creators. Personalisation algorithms integrated into Meta Ads, Google Ads, Mailchimp AI and other platforms allow content to be precisely targeted based on user behaviour and interests. This is particularly important in social media marketing, where real-time solutions and personalised communication drive campaign success. Data analytics and predictive solutions such as

3. Despite the significant advantages, important challenges have also emerged, such as the rapid change in AI, the need for specialist training, the need for investment, and data protection and ethical issues. Effective application of the AI in social networks requires not only technological expertise but also a continuous adaptation process to ensure that tools are adapted to specific communication needs.

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